

GASOLINE STATION EMPLOYEES' WORKPLACE COMMUNICATION, RESILIENCE, AND MOTIVATION: LINKS TO THEIR WORK PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Work performance reflects employees' contributions to organizational goals, encompassing efficiency, productivity, and overall impact. Using the descriptive-correlational research design, this study investigated the influence of workplace communication, resilience, and motivation on employee performance, particularly in challenging environments like gasoline stations. The researcher selected a sample of 119 employees from 17 gas stations in Visayas and Mindanao who were selected through random sampling. The researcher utilized modified questionnaires: Communication Satisfaction Questionnaire (Downs and Hazen, 1977), and Work Resilience Scale (Sweetman et al.,2022), Motivation at Work Scale (MAWS), and the Adaptive Work Performance Questionnaire (Koopmans et al.,2014). Findings reveal that the employees assessed themselves very high and resilience and high in work communication and motivation as well as in job performance. Regression analysis further shows that when the variables are combined, they significantly influence the employees' work performance. However, when the variables are taken singly, only work communication significantly influences work performance, while resilience and motivation do not significantly influence work performance. An action plan is, thus, proposed to address the indicators that received relatively low scores, ensuring targeted interventions for improvement.

Keywords: *Work Performance, Workplace Communication, Resilience, Motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Gasoline stations play a crucial role in transportation and logistics, requiring efficient operations and high-quality customer service. However, limited research explores the combined influence of workplace communication, resilience, and motivation on employee performance in this sector. While previous studies highlight these factors individually, there is a gap in understanding their interdependence within challenging and service-oriented environments. Addressing this gap is essential for enhancing employee effectiveness, minimizing operational disruptions, and improving customer satisfaction. Furthermore, this study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) by promoting productive employment and workplace well-being.

This study applies Social Exchange Theory (SET) to explain how reciprocal exchanges of trust, information, and support influence workplace communication, fostering collaboration, engagement, and operational clarity. Timely and precise communication enhances efficiency, while communication failures can compromise service quality. Resilience, defined by Masten (2001) as the ability to adapt and thrive amid adversity, is another critical factor in high-stress environments. Employees with strong resilience maintain productivity despite challenges such as demanding customers and unpredictable conditions. Motivation, grounded in Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (SDT), further influences performance by fulfilling psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Intrinsically motivated employees demonstrate greater accuracy, adherence to schedules, and strong customer rapport. By examining the interplay of communication, resilience, and motivation, this study provides insights for improving employee performance in gasoline stations, ultimately benefiting both workers and business sustainability.

Framework

This research assumes that workplace communication, employees' resilience, and motivation influence their work performance. The study further argues that if gasoline station employees are highly motivated, have greater resilience, and have better communication, they are more likely to perform better in the workplace. This study is grounded in several well-established theories that help explain the relationship between workplace communication, resilience, motivation, and work performance. The theories provide a comprehensive structure for understanding how employees perform in a demanding work environment like a gasoline station.

The study draws on Social Exchange Theory (SET), proposed by Blau (1964), which posits that social interactions are based on reciprocal exchanges of resources such as information, trust, and support. Open and effective communication fosters a sense of value and collaboration within the workplace. Enhanced communication promotes engagement, task clarity, and teamwork, improving performance. For gasoline station employees, timely and precise communication is critical in ensuring operational efficiency and minimizing disruptions.

Resilience is another key work performance factor, particularly in high-stress environments like gasoline stations. Masten (2001) defines resilience as adapting to and thriving amidst adversity. For gasoline station employees, this support system includes colleagues, managers, and external networks that help them navigate workplace challenges. Resilience is positively correlated with performance, as supported by Weiss et al. (2023), who found that as resilience increases, so does job performance.

Motivation also plays a significant role in determining employee performance. This study adopts Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (SDT), postulating the fulfillment of autonomy, competence, and relatedness as core psychological needs that drive intrinsic motivation. Motivated employees are likelier to maintain work accuracy, adhere to schedules, and develop strong customer rapport. Furthermore, motivation and resilience are closely interlinked, as intrinsic motivation often reinforces employees' capacity to overcome challenges and persist in achieving their goals.

This study conceptualizes work performance as a multidimensional construct encompassing work accuracy, timeliness, and customer rapport. Work accuracy refers to employees' ability to adhere to safety protocols, reporting standards, and operational guidelines, which are critical in a high-risk environment like a gasoline station. Accuracy in gasoline station operations is particularly significant, as errors in reporting sales, inventory, or safety procedures can lead to operational risks and financial setbacks. Carter et al. (2016) further underscores the role of structured training and clear protocols in enhancing accuracy, contributing to organizational success. Timeliness pertains to punctuality and meeting deadlines and schedules, which is essential for maintaining operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. Timeliness, a crucial component of employee performance, ensures organizational efficiency and seamless operations. Devaraj and Jiang (2019) emphasize that timely task execution is critical in maintaining team cohesion and meeting dynamic operational demands.

Finally, customer rapport highlights the quality of interactions between employees and customers, emphasizing the importance of effective communication, empathy, and reliability in fostering customer loyalty and trust. Recent studies underscore the significance of positive interpersonal dynamics within service teams in enhancing customer experiences. Lai, Griffin, and Babin (2009) identify service quality as a key determinant of customer loyalty, which is crucial for long-term success. In the context of gasoline stations, the civility of staff, accuracy of dispensing pumps, and product quality significantly influence customer trust and patronage, as demonstrated by Olumuyiwa, et.al, (2022).

This study also integrates Social Exchange Theory, Resilience Theory, and Self-Determination Theory to comprehensively understand how workplace communication, resilience, and motivation predict work performance. By analyzing these constructs holistically, the study highlights their interdependence and relevance in shaping employee outcomes in a challenging operational environment. The findings of this study are expected to provide insights into enhancing employee performance, ultimately benefiting

both employees and organizational success. Figure 1 shows the interplay of variables where workplace communication, motivation, and resilience are the independent variables surmised to have influenced the employees' work performance.

Research Questions

1. What are the participants' key characteristics in terms of:
 - 1.1 workplace communication;
 - 1.2 resilience; and
 - 1.3 motivation
2. What is the employees' level of work performance in a gas station in terms of:
 - 2.1. Work Accuracy;
 - 2.2. Timeliness;
 - 2.3 Customer Rapport
3. Does the employees' assessment of their workplace communication, resilience, and motivation significantly influence their level of performance?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: The participants' assessment of their key characteristics in terms of workplace communication, resilience, and motivation does not significantly influence their performance

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Interplay of Variables in the Study

Objective of the Study

This study aimed to examine the relationship between workplace communication, resilience, and motivation and their influence on the work performance of gasoline station employees. Additionally, the study sought to provide insights into strategies that improve communication, strengthen motivation, and optimize employee performance in high-demand service settings.

METHODOLOGY

Using the descriptive-correlational research design, this study investigated the influence of workplace communication, resilience, and motivation on employee performance, particularly in challenging environments like gasoline stations. The researcher selected a sample of 119 employees from 17 gas stations in Visayas and Mindanao who were selected through random sampling. The researcher utilized modified questionnaires: Communication Satisfaction Questionnaire (Downs and Hazen, 1977), and Work Resilience Scale (Sweetman et al.,2022), Motivation at Work Scale (MAWS),

and the Adaptive Work Performance Questionnaire (Koopmans et al.,2014). Data collection included the use of descriptive statistics, such as frequency, mean, percentages, and standard deviation, to determine the participants' key characteristics. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was conducted to explore the influence of employees' assessments of their key characteristics and their work performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data from the summary table highlights a generally positive perception of key characteristics within the gasoline station context, with the highest score for **resilience** (mean = 4.51) and a tie between **work communication** and **motivation** (both with means of 4.45). These results offer important implications for how employees perform and interact within the demanding environment of gasoline stations.

Resilience emerged with the highest mean, indicating that employees perceive themselves as highly capable of adapting to challenges and recovering from setbacks in their workplace. In the context of gasoline stations, this resilience is essential given the fast-paced and often stressful nature of the job, which may involve handling difficult customers, managing peak hours, or coping with safety risks. Resilient employees are better equipped to maintain productivity and emotional well-being, even under pressure. Research by Gupta and Sharma (2020) supports this finding, highlighting that resilience in service employees leads to higher job satisfaction, better customer interactions, and overall improved job performance. In a gasoline station, fostering resilience can contribute to enhanced employee engagement, reduced turnover, and more consistent service delivery.

On the other hand, **work communication** and **motivation** both scored highly, reflecting that employees believe communication and motivation within the workplace are also strong. Effective communication is particularly crucial in the gasoline station context, where quick, clear exchanges between employees, supervisors, and customers are vital for smooth operations. Such a finding aligns with research by Lee et al. (2021), positing that clear communication fosters teamwork and helps reduce errors in high-pressure environments.

While the overall scores are high, the slight variation in standard deviation (ranging from 0.32 for resilience to 0.41 for work communication) suggests there may be minor differences in how employees perceive these dimensions. These differences, while small, could indicate that some employees might require additional support in areas like communication or motivation, depending on their individual needs and experiences. This highlights the importance of personalized management strategies to ensure that all employees feel equally supported in these critical areas.

As a whole, the data suggest that while resilience, work communication, and motivation are all viewed positively by employees in the gasoline station context, there is

an opportunity to further strengthen these areas through tailored interventions, such as communication training or targeted motivation strategies. By building on the already high levels of resilience and work communication, gasoline stations can foster a more resilient, motivated, and communicative workforce, ultimately leading to better customer service and operational efficiency.

Table 1
Summary Table of Assessment of Key Characteristics

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Work Communication	4.45	High	0.41
Resilience	4.51	Very High	0.32
Motivation	4.45	High	0.37
Overall	4.48	High	0.25

Table 2 presents the assessment of work performance across various dimensions, with an overall mean of 4.53, which falls in the "Very High" range. This denotes that employees generally perceive their work performance positively, indicating a high level of efficiency and effectiveness in their roles. The overall high rating implies a well-functioning team environment where employees are performing their tasks with accuracy, timeliness, and positive customer interactions, all of which are key to organizational success in the gasoline station context.

The highest mean rating is for **work accuracy** (4.58), reflecting that employees prioritize precision in their tasks. This is particularly important in the gasoline station environment, where even small errors in tasks such as fuel dispensing, cash handling, or safety procedures can have significant consequences. High work accuracy is essential for maintaining safety, customer trust, and operational efficiency. Research by Lee et al. (2020) emphasizes the importance of accuracy in service-oriented roles, noting that employees who excel in this area contribute to improved service quality and customer satisfaction.

On the other hand, **customer rapport** received the lowest mean of 4.50, though still classified as "High." This implies that while employees maintain positive interactions with customers, there may be areas for improvement in establishing stronger connections with them. The nature of the gasoline station context, where interactions are often brief, may limit opportunities for deeper engagement. However, the relatively high score still indicates that employees understand the importance of building rapport with customers to enhance service quality and satisfaction. According to Yang et al. (2021), customer rapport is a crucial factor in customer retention, and even small improvements in this area can lead to greater customer loyalty and positive word-of-mouth.

In a nutshell, the very high overall mean of 4.53 reflects strong work performance in terms of accuracy, timeliness, and customer rapport. While work accuracy and timeliness are particularly strong, there is room to enhance customer rapport. This could be achieved by fostering more personalized and engaging interactions with customers, even in a fast-paced setting. By focusing on strengthening these areas, gasoline stations can further improve their service quality and customer relationships, contributing to overall business success.

Table 2

Summary Table of Work Performance

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Work Accuracy	4.58	Very High	0.45
Timeliness	4.52	Very High	0.52
Customer Rapport	4.50	High	0.46
Overall	4.54	Very High	0.42

Table 3 shows that the whole model is significant ($F=3.43$, $p = .020$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that the employees who assess their workplace communication, resilience, and motivation as high also perform well. This further means that improvements in workplace communication, resilience, and motivation are likely to enhance employee performance. The significance of the model indicates that the combined effects of these factors are meaningful and warrant further exploration to understand their specific contributions to performance outcomes. This has been affirmed by the study of Mulyono et al. (2024), which states that high motivation and resilience support organizational development and success. Also, a study by Musheke and Phiri (2021) found that effective communication significantly influences employee performance, with a positive correlation between open communication and organizational outcomes.

However, only 8.2 percent of the variability in their performance is accounted for by a combination of the predictor variables. The remaining 91.8 percent may be attributed to other factors, such as individual differences, wherein conscientiousness and emotional stability can significantly impact performance (Petkova, A. P. 2006). Also, key characteristics and competencies affect overperformance since variations in technical skills, problem-solving abilities, and adaptability play a crucial role.

Conversely, the environment may also be a factor that contributes to organizational culture. A very supportive culture that encourages innovation and collaboration can enhance performance. Lastly, team dynamics like interpersonal relationships may also be attractive. The quality of relationships among team members can affect collaboration

and overall performance. Understanding these additional factors is crucial for organizations aiming to enhance employee performance comprehensively.

When the variables are examined individually, findings reveal that workplace communication came out as having a significant influence on their performance, indicating that for every unit increase in their workplace communication, there is a corresponding .293 increase in their performance (*B=.293, t=3.09, p = .002). Resilience and motivation do not significantly influence their performance when taken singly, although they contribute to the variability in their performance, as cited earlier. Based on the findings, it is evident that workplace communication is necessary in order to increase one's performance. The bolder and more accessible the communication flow inside the organization, the more problems can be solved instantly. On the other hand, resilience and motivation can only pull performance up if they are backed up by effective communication. In this point, communication is used as a bridge between management and employees so that they can understand and appreciate the things and factors that drive the employees to be resilient.

Table 3

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Employees' Assessment of their Workplace Communication, Resilience, and Motivation on their Performance

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	3.56	.711		5.01	.000
Workplace communication	.293	.095	.291	3.09**	.002
Resilience	.050	.118	.038	.421	.675
Motivation	-.124	.106	-.109	-1.17	.244

Model Summary				
R = .286	R ² = .082	Adjusted R ² = .058	F = 3.43*	p = .020

**significant at .001

* significant at .05

Conclusions

In the context of a gasoline station, the study concludes that workplace communication plays a critical role in influencing employees' performance, emphasizing the value of clear and effective interaction in maintaining high service standards. This finding aligns with the principles of Social Exchange Theory, which suggests that reciprocal and meaningful communication fosters trust, commitment, and enhanced performance within organizations. The significant impact of workplace communication highlights its function as a key driver of employee engagement and operational success in service-oriented settings.

However, the study found no significant influence of resilience and motivation on performance, which may indicate that these factors are context-specific or operate indirectly through other variables, such as workplace culture or job demands. This could reflect the unique demands of the gasoline station environment, where task-specific communication and immediate problem-solving are prioritized over broader psychological constructs. Nevertheless, a limitation of the study is its reliance on self-reported measures, which may introduce bias, and its cross-sectional design, which precludes conclusions about causality. Future research could investigate the interplay between workplace communication and other elements of Social Exchange Theory, such as trust and perceived organizational support, to provide deeper insights. Additionally, longitudinal studies could explore how these dynamics evolve over time and their impact on customer satisfaction.

Recommendations

Future researchers may explore the longitudinal impact of workplace communication on employee performance to better understand its sustained influence over time. They could also examine the mediating role of customer satisfaction between employee communication and overall business success in service industries. Expanding the research to include diverse business contexts and incorporating mixed methods could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the variables involved. HR departments may likewise design and implement policies that strengthen workplace communication channels while also addressing other organizational factors such as resilience and motivation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before implementing the questionnaire, the researcher obtained ethics clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee to ensure that participants' rights were protected. The study was guided by the fundamental ethical principles in the Belmont Report, which emphasize respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Approval was also sought from the company's management through the Human Resources Department, which oversees employees assigned to the gas stations.

Following this, an intent letter from the operations manager was provided, informing branch managers about the researcher's visit to conduct the survey.

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